

Kinetics of Thermal Dehydration of Hydroxide Hydrogels of Chromium, Manganese and Cobalt

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Manuscript received 28 February 1992, revised 27 November 1992, accepted 7 January 1993

Kinetics of thermal dehydration of synthetic hydroxide hydrogel of chromium, manganese and cobalt were studied in the temperature range 70 - 450°. The kinetic data and activation energies were different for different stages of dehydration. Activation energy increased progressively with DTA peak temperature in case of all the hydroxide hydrogels.

Hydroxides precipitated by bases from aqueous solution of their respective salts are commonly amorphous. Water is an integral part of the gel structure. These non-crystalline hydroxides contain water which may be regarded as the extreme case of broken bond water in which the particle size of the solid to which the water is linked, is extremely small. In most of the hydroxides there seems to be a force of attraction between the hydroxyl ions of adjacent layers which may explain their insolubility in water.

Gelatinous hydroxides of chromium, manganese and cobalt are of interest because of their industrial importance in preparing various materials. Willstatter *et al.*¹ investigated various types of gel, in most cases precipitated from alum or aluminium sulphate solution by ammonia below 60°. Imelik *et al.*² found that amorphous gels precipitated from salts by a base at pH 7 are impure and contain a significant amount of anions. Precipitates obtained at a more alkaline pH (about 9), contain less anions but are not strictly amorphous. They showed that the preparation method of the gels influences their morphology. Mitra *et al.*³ found that rate constant during zeolitic dehydration followed an inverse relationship with total water content. Zeolitic rehydration was found to involve diffusion of water molecules⁴ and the activation energies for the natural material were markedly higher than those for synthetic material.

Results and Discussion

The three hydrogels as synthesised under present experimental conditions were amorphous in nature as evidenced by X-ray analysis (figure not shown). The DTA curve of all the three hydroxide hydrogels showed two endothermic peaks (figure not shown) which were associated with the expulsion of water from the structure—not all from the lattice, some being loosely bound. The temperatures for studying the kinetics of dehydration were selected accordingly and the rate studies were carried out separately at initial and final

stages of dehydration. In the higher temperature range, the effect of loosely bound water was eliminated by preheating the sample at a particular temperature.

Isothermal dehydration curves (figures not shown) showed exponential behaviour and therefore first order kinetics were suggested. The method of Guggenheim⁵ was adopted to calculate the initial amount of water (L_∞) which can be removed at the experimental temperature and also the rate constant K_1 for the initial part of dehydration, using equation (1),

$$\log \Delta L = \frac{-K_1 t}{2.303} + \log L_\infty [1 - \exp(-K_1 \Delta t)] \quad (1)$$

where ΔL is the difference between the mass loss at time $(t + \Delta t)$ and time t . The time interval Δt between the two sets of readings was kept fixed at a

Fig. 1. $\log \Delta L$ plots of chromium hydroxide hydrogel at different temperatures.

value greater than twice the time for 50% dehydration. Using equation (1), the rate constant was calculated from the slope of linear plots of $\log \Delta L$ vs t (Fig. 1). Knowing Δt and having obtained K_1 from the slope, L_∞ was determined from the intercept on the $\log \Delta L$ axis. The values of K_1 and L_∞ (Table 1) in all the three hydroxide

TABLE 1—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (K_1) AND L_∞ AS DETERMINED FROM $\log \Delta L$ VS TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	Dehydration stage	Temp. °C	K_1 min ⁻¹	L_∞ (g)		
Chromium hydroxide	First	70	0.023 5	0.043 4		
		107	0.040 5	0.055 1		
		130	0.069 1	0.063 6		
		160	0.103 6	0.075 5		
		190	0.158 9	0.091 4		
	Second	190	0.229 3	0.165 4		
		220	0.391 5	0.168 2		
		250	0.460 6	0.188 3		
		280	0.506 6	0.205 4		
		310	0.568 0	0.212 4		
Manganese hydroxide	First	70	0.066 7	0.020 7		
		100	0.110 5	0.023 8		
		130	0.175 0	0.032 5		
		160	0.244 1	0.053 4		
		190	0.316 6	0.066 8		
	Second	250	0.276 3	0.045 5		
		280	0.322 4	0.071 4		
		310	0.345 4	0.082 2		
		Cobalt hydroxide	First	70	0.201 5	0.007 3
				100	0.240 1	0.010 0
130	0.276 3			0.014 2		
160	0.313 7			0.017 8		
190	0.351 2			0.023 5		
Second	330	0.460 6	0.027 9			
	360	0.483 6	0.029 1			
	396	0.552 7	0.041 6			
	420	0.587 2	0.048 7			
	450	0.621 8	0.056 2			

hydrogels at intermediate temperatures in the initial stage interpolate well. The activation energy was calculated from the usual Arrhenius plots of the rate constants (Fig. 2).

The temperatures used for studying dehydration kinetics were selected from the DTA curve of all the three hydrogels, where endothermic peak temperatures were found to be 130, 225° for chromium, 110, 250° for manganese and 100, 225° for cobalt.

L_∞ values were determined for initial and final dehydration stages, their sum corresponds with the total equilibrium water content in the original hydrogel structure. The L_∞ values in the final dehydration stages in all the three hydroxide hydrogels were higher than in the initial stage. In the initial dehydration part of 1st stage, normally capillary and loosely bound surface water is expelled, and in the final part strongly bound lattice water is removed. This non-homogeneous type of dehydration involves processes such as the combination of surface hydroxyls with H^+ ion to

Fig. 2. Arrhenius plots at the initial and final stage of dehydration for synthetic hydroxide hydroxels: (O) initial $Cr(OH)_3$, (Δ) initial $Mn(OH)_2$, (\square) initial $Co(OH)_2$ and (X) final $Cr(OH)_3$.

form water, cation migration and change in oxygen bonding. The rate constant values for both the dehydration stage were found to be a direct function of temperature, i.e. the reaction rate of the gel increased with an increase in temperature.

The limits of applicability of first order law for dehydration of chromium, manganese and cobalt hydroxide hydrogels were determined for initial and final dehydration stages through the linearity of the plots of $\log (L_\infty - L)/L_\infty$ vs time and the results are given in Table 2. It is seen that results for intermediate temperatures in both the stages interpolate well.

The general trend as it appears from an analysis of the results of Table 2, is the existence of a direct relationship between the extent of validity and temperature. Some deviations as observed at higher temperature appear to be due to heterogeneity in the distribution of water molecules as well as the enhanced diffusion barrier created by the dehydrated phase. When the temperature is increased the hydrogel, which remains unreactive in isolation at the later stages of the lower temperature treatment, becomes active with respect to the interaction due to increased lattice vibration.

Values of the rate constant K_2 for the final stage of dehydration were calculated from equation (2),

$$K_2 = \frac{dL/dt}{(L_\infty - L)} \quad (2)$$

TABLE 2—EXTENT OF VALIDITY OF FIRST ORDER LAW AS DETERMINED FROM $\log(L_\alpha - L)/L - \alpha$ VS TIME PLOTS

Hydrogel	Dehydration stage	Temp. °C	% Dehydration upto which first order law valid	
Chromium hydroxide	First	70	91.30	
		100	92.06	
		130	93.06	
		160	97.02	
		190	98.18	
	Second	190	67.4	
		220	60.37	
		250	58.58	
		280	57.99	
		310	57.43	
Manganese hydroxide	First	70	91.17	
		100	92.14	
		130	93.06	
		160	74.42	
		190	63.46	
	Second	250	92.93	
		280	88.12	
		310	79.05	
Cobalt hydroxide	First	70	91.09	
		100	92.06	
		130	92.91	
		160	93.11	
		190	94.47	
	Second	330	92.80	
		360	93.69	
		390	94.63	
		420	95.73	
		450	97.16	

where dL/dt is the slope of the weight-loss vs time curve at a point of 70% dehydration and L the actual loss at that time. The choice of 70% dehydration in case of chromium hydroxide hydrogel was made because it appears that in no case did the rate of dehydration follow first order kinetics beyond this point at the final stage of dehydration although at the initial stage of dehydration it was more than 90%. The calculated values of rate constant (K_2) of dehydration at final stage of dehydration of only chromium hydroxide hydrogel are given in Table 3. K_2 values were

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (K_2) AT FINAL DEHYDRATION STAGE OF CHROMIUM HYDROXIDE HYDROGEL

Hydrogel	Temp. °C	K_2 min ⁻¹
Chromium hydroxide	190	0.161 1
	220	0.208 0
	250	0.258 4
	280	0.325 9
	310	0.389 1

not calculated for manganese and cobalt hydroxide hydrogels because first order kinetics were followed in both of them to the extent of more than 90% in both initial and final stages of dehydration. K_2 values were lower than the K_1 values (second stage) indicating a slower rate of dehydration towards the end of final stage. This might be due

to the fact that at the end of first order range, when a significant amount of water has been expelled, the residual water concentration is so low that the interactions of these structurally isolated water molecules faces a greater barrier. The above dehydration phenomenon is a special case of proton tunnelling. As more and more water molecules are removed, the positive charge density of the samples increases as the charge of the metal cation is dispersed in this case over fewer no of molecular centres. Hence in phase O—H stretching and out-of-phase O—H bending frequency decrease as in both these cases, the electrons of the bond have to move against the positively charged force fields. As such the closeness of the protons of the neighbouring OH⁻ groups decreases; hence their chances of interaction and consequently the rate of formation of water molecule decreases and so the rate constant decreases.

The calculated values of activation energy from Arrhenius plots (Fig. 2) are given in Table 4. It is seen that in case of chromium, manganese and cobalt hydroxide hydrogels, the activation energy in the earlier (i.e. first order kinetics) part of dehydration was mostly concerned with the channel water in the hydrogel structure, whereas in case of chromium hydroxide hydrogel only in the final part (i.e. 70% completion) of dehydration, the reaction includes the expulsion of strongly bound water. The removal of hydroxyl groups from chromium hydroxide hydrogel required higher energy.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGY FOR INITIAL AND FINAL PARTS OF DEHYDRATION IN INITIAL AND FINAL STAGES

Hydrogel	Dehydration stage	Activation energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	
		Initial part of dehydration (first order kinetics)	Final part of dehydration (dehydration stage 70% complete)
Chromium hydroxide	First	4.91	2.37
	Final	—	3.84
Manganese hydroxide	First	4.07	2.28
	Final	—	—
Cobalt hydroxide	First	1.46	2.10
	Final	—	—

The above results broadly indicate that the dehydration rates of hydroxide hydrogels of chromium, manganese and cobalt depend on the nature of cation and on the porous channel structure and framework of the gel.

Conclusion: The water in the chromium, manganese and cobalt hydroxide hydrogels is bonded with different energies as exhibited by different peaks in the DTA curves. The major dehydration step in case of manganese and cobalt occurred according to the first order kinetics, whereas in

case of chromium hydroxide hydrogel, above 70% completion of initial stage, these kinetics are no longer followed and the rate of dehydration fell. The activation energy in the earlier part of dehydration corresponds to expulsion of the channel water, whereas in the final part of dehydration in case of chromium includes the expulsion of strongly bound water. It may be added that the above kinetic data will be very much useful in controlling the dehydration of the hydrogel for conversion to active oxide powders as otherwise the excess energy may lead to agglomerate formation.

Experimental

Chromium, manganese and cobalt hydroxide hydrogels were prepared by the process of wet interaction of their salts with $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}-\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ with thorough stirring at pH 9. After proper aging the gels were processed by standard methods to remove impurities. Finally the materials were

dried at 60° , ground, sieved to $-20+50$ B.S. sieve size and stored in a thermostat at $30\pm 1^\circ$. Kinetics of dehydration of all the three hydroxide hydrogel samples were studied by carrying out isothermal experiments in a thermogravimetric apparatus⁶.

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